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Review Article

Phytoconstituents And Pharmacological Activities of *Phyllanthus emblica*

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ABSTRACT

Phyllanthus emblica, commonly referred to as Indian gooseberry or amla, has received a lot of attention recently due to its diverse phytochemical composition and associated pharmacological characteristics. This paper summarizes the phytochemistry, pharmacological characteristics, and historical uses of *Phyllanthus emblica* fruits. Through a careful evaluation of the literature, this review highlights the rich phytochemical profile of *Phyllanthus emblica*, which includes flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and polyphenolic compounds. *Phyllanthus emblica* fruits bioactive composition—particularly their high levels of polyphenol and vitamin C—is what gives them their hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. *Phyllanthus emblica* is a natural resource that has a lot of potential for use in pharmacological research and complementary and alternative medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Approximately half of India's higher blooming plant species are medicinal plants, which account for approximately 8000 species. Traditional remedies, which are largely derived from plant sources, have played an important role in the treatment of many chronic conditions, including diabetes, particularly in countries such as India¹⁻³.

A survey by the World Health Organisation found that 80% of people in underdeveloped nations get their main medical care nearly entirely from traditional medicine⁴. People have been employing herbal medicines to treat a range of disorders since the beginning of time since plants are regarded to be either nontoxic or less hazardous than manmade drugs⁵.

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Phyllanthus emblica Linn., a member of the Euphorbiaceae family, is found in most tropical and subtropical nations⁶. As to the two primary Ayurvedic classic books, Sushruta Samhita and Charaka Samhita, *P. emblica* is considered "the best among the sour fruits" and "the best among rejuvenators". It is a key component of significant medical preparations such as Triphala and Chyawanprash, a general tonic that enhances mental and physical health for people of all ages⁷. Pharmacological activities of *p.emblica* includes anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, anti-diabetic, neuroprotective and hepatoprotective ,etc.. However, the pharmacological properties of *P. emblica* are frequently studied in relation to Triphala, an Ayurvedic preparation consisting of equal parts of three fruits from medicinal plants: *P. emblica*, *Terminellia chebula*, and *T. belerica*^{8 9 10}.

PLANT DESCRIPTION: -

SYNONYMS: -

Phyllanthus emblica – Synonyms are Balakka, Amlaki, *Emblica officinalis*, Indian gooseberry, Amla, *Emblic myrobalan*, *UsirikayAdiphala*.

This includes the fresh and dried fruits of the Euphorbiaceae family plant *Emblica officinalis*

Gaerth (*Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.).

Fig:-An image of Phyllanthus emblica

MORPHOLOGY: -

The amla tree, a small to medium-sized deciduous tree, can grow to be 8 to 18 meters tall. Its thin, light grey bark exfoliates in tiny, irregular flakes, revealing a new, different-colored surface beneath the old bark. The main stem has an average diameter of 70 cm. Usually, the main trunk is separated from the base by two to seven scaffolds¹¹. The leaves are closely packed in pinnate faishon³ and measure 10–13 mm in length¹² and 3 mm in width, giving the branches a fluffy appearance overall. Following fruit setting, leaves begin to grow. The flowers are 4 to 5 mm long, pale green, unisexual, and borne in clusters of 6 to 10 on the leaf axils. Fleshy, nearly globose in shape, the fruits measure 2.1-2.4 cm in diameter, 5.3-5.7 g in weight, and 4.5-5.0 mL in capacity. Fruit has a six-ribbed stone that splits into three segment^[12], each of which contains two seeds. The seeds are 4-5 mm long and 2-3 mm wide, and they weigh between 572 and 590m^{12 13}.

Colour	When matured, green turns brick red or pale yellow.
Odour	None.
Taste	Sore and Astringent.
Shape	Fruits are depressed, globose.
Size	1.5 – 2.5 cm in diameter.

TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION:-

It includes,

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Angiosperma [flowerimg plant]

Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Malpighiales
Family	Phyllanthaceae
Genus	Phyllanthus
Species	emblica

PHYTOCONSTITUENTS:-

"Phyllembelin" is the active chemical identified by Indian scientists as having a substantial pharmacological impact in amla. The fruit is abundant in quercetin, phyllaemblic compounds, gallic acid, tannins, flavonoids, pectin, and vitamin C, in addition to a range of other polyphenolic compounds. Terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and other phytochemical components have been shown to have positive biological properties^{14,15}. The fruits, leaves, and bark all have a high tannin content. The root contains lupeol and ellagic acid, whereas the bark contains leucodelphinidin. The seeds yield a steady (16%) oil with a brownish-yellow tint. Its components are linolenic (8.8%), linoleic (44.0%), oleic (28.4%), stearic (2.15%), palmitic (3.0%), and myristic (1.0%) fatty acids¹⁶.

This plant contains hydrolysable tannins such as eblicanin A, eblicanin B, punigluconin, and pedunculagin¹⁷. Flavonoids include Kaempferol 3-O-alpha-L-(6-methyl) rhamnopyranoside and Kaempferol 3-O-alpha-L-(6-ethyl) rhamnopyranoside." alkaloids, including phytollantine, phytollantidine Gallic acid, ellagic acid, 1-O-galloyl-beta-D-glucose, 3,6-di-O-galloyl-D-glucose, chebulinic acid, quercetin, chebulagic acid, corilagin, and isostrictinin were isolated from Phyllanthusemblica fruits. A new acylated glucoside was isolated from the methanolic extract of P.emblica leaves¹⁸. The molecules luteolin 4-O-neohesperidoside, gallic acid, methyl gallate, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 penta-

Ogalloylglucose were combined to form apigenin 7-O-(6"-butyryl-beta)-glucopyranoside¹⁹. P. emblica seeds have phosphatides, fixed oil, and a trace amount of essential oil. Moreover, the leaves include chebulagic, ellagic, gallic, and chebulinic acids. Phyllaemblic acid, a new highly oxygenated norbisabolane, was isolated from P.emblica roots and its structure was fully characterised using chemical and spectroscopic methods. Ellagic acid and lupeol are detected in P.emblica roots²⁰.

Fruit: Protein 0.5%, fat 0.1%, mineral matter 0.7%, fibre 3.4%, carbohydrates 14.1%, nicotinic acid (0.2 mg/100g), gallic acid, phyllembelin, phyllembelic acid, emblicokellagic acid, pectin 725-277²¹⁻²², SOD 482²³, 14 units/g, putranjivain, and quercetin, were all present in the mixture²⁴.

Seeds: The seeds of the Indian gooseberry contain a fixed oil, phosphatides, and an essential oil. The seeds yields a fixed oil (16%) that is brownish yellow. Linolenic acid (8.8%), linoleic (44.0%), oleic (28.4%), stearic (2.15%), palmitic (3.0%), and myristic acid were also present. There are proteolytic and lipolytic chemicals present²⁵.

Leaves: The bark and leaves have a high concentration of tannins. The leaves contain the alkaloids phyllantidine and phyllantine, gallic acid, ellagic acid, chebulic, chebulagic, and chebulinic acids, as well as the gallotannin an lie acid²⁶.

Constituent	Type	Function/Properties
Vitamin C	Vitamin	Antioxidant, boosts immune system
Tannins	Polyphenols	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory properties

Flavonoids	Polyphenols	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, supports heart health
Gallic Acid	Phenolic Acid	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-cancer properties
Ellagic Acid	Phenolic Compound	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, potential anti-cancer
Beta-Sitosterol	Phytosterol	Cholesterol-lowering effects, anti-inflammatory
Alkaloids	Alkaloids	Various pharmacological effects
Saponins	Glycosides	Antioxidant, immune-boosting properties
Essential Oils	Volatile Compounds	Antimicrobial, aromatic properties

COLLECTION AND EXTRACTION:-

The plant *Phyllanthus emblica* was harvested for its leaves and branches.

Harvesting & Selection of Plant Parts:

Phyllanthus emblica is a plant that has received significant study for its therapeutic properties. Its leaves and branches are rich in bioactive substances such as flavonoids, polyphenols, and tannins, which enhance its antioxidant and beneficial properties²⁷.

Drying: In botanical extraction, drying at moderate temperatures, such as 50°C, is popular because it reduces moisture while maintaining heat-sensitive phytochemicals²⁸. By taking this procedure, the extract quality is protected from microbiological contamination and enzymatic deterioration²⁹.

Grinding: By reducing the dry material to a fine powder, the surface area is increased, which makes it easier to extract chemicals when combined with a solvent³⁰. To increase consistency and standardise the extraction procedure, a particle size of 0.5 mm is frequently employed³¹.

Aqueous Extraction and Heating: Water is a common solvent since it is safe, economical, and effective at removing polar substances like polyphenols. While temperatures below boiling are usually employed to protect heat-sensitive ingredients, heating to 95°C improves extraction by dissolving cell walls and improving solubility³².

Filtration: Whatman® No. 1 paper creates a clear solution for additional testing by efficiently removing bigger plant residues while permitting small, dissolved chemicals to flow through³³.

Storage: In order to preserve the extract's bioactivity, it must be kept at -20°C. This is because low temperatures prevent microbial development and chemical degradation, maintaining the extract's quality for in vitro research³⁴.

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES:-

1. Anti cancer Activity:-

Cancer is still a major worldwide health concern, which drives scientists to investigate new drugs and therapies that reduce cancer cell survival, prevent angiogenesis, stop proliferation, and limit metastasis³⁵. Several flavonoids and phytochemical compounds have emerged as promising cancer treatments in the recent years.

A thorough analysis of the *Phyllanthus emblica* fruit extract's mode of action was conducted. In relation to cholangiocarcinoma, the ethanolic extract of *Phyllanthus emblica*, the anti-proliferative properties were evaluated³⁶. With an IC50 value of 52.2 µg/mL and a notable induction of apoptosis, the results demonstrated the extract's cytotoxic capability on the KKV-452 CCA cell line. In addition, at 25 and 50 µg/mL, the ethanolic extract of *Phyllanthus emblica* bark significantly reduced cell migration, with decreases of 425% and 32.9%, respectively, in comparison to untreated cells. *Phyllanthus emblica* bark extract's phenolic acid and flavonoid content were thought to be responsible for these anticancer actions.

2. Immunomodulatory Activity:-

The immune system's activity serves as a powerful defence against both internal and external hazards. Due to their immunomodulatory properties, numerous plants have been utilised to cure human

illnesses from ancient times. It was discovered that medicinal plants improved the function of natural killer (NK) cells and stimulated the immune system. In mice with tumours, FPE extended life expectancy by 35% by doubling the function of splenic NK cells³⁷⁻³⁸. Swiss albino rats given 100 and 200 mg/kg of *P. emblica* fruit extracts for 19 days likewise showed a dose-dependent immunomodulatory response, according to Suja et al. (2009). The fruit extracts dramatically raised the mice's leukocyte count, lymphocyte distribution percentage, hemagglutination antibody titer, and delayed hypersensitivity. Along with macrophage phagocytes, the aqueous extract of FPE also produced humoral and cell-mediated immunity³⁸. Because of its immunomodulatory properties, *P. emblica* demonstrated its numerous uses for preventing and treating a range of illnesses.

3. Anti oxidant Activity:-

Natural products derived from food sources contain a variety of free radical scavenging components. The ascorbic acid content of *P. emblica* was thought to be the cause of its antioxidant properties until 1990³⁹. In 1996, it was determined that *P. emblica* contained no ascorbic acid at all, and that its antioxidant activities were attributable to hydrolysable tannins such as emblicanins¹⁷. Components such as ascorbic acid in avoiding oxidative damage. The aqueous extract of FPE considerably increased antioxidant capacity by boosting the levels of GSH and antioxidant system enzymes such as catalase, superoxide dismutase, GSH peroxidase, GSH reductase, and GSH S-transferase.

The antioxidant potential of sesquiterpenoids and diphenyl ether-like compounds from FPE was demonstrated in similar studies conducted by different research groups using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models to determine the antioxidant activity of *P. emblica* polyphenolic constituents including flavonoids and tannins⁴⁰. Gallic acid, ellagic acid,

and corilagin are polyphenolic compounds that have been shown to have the antioxidant ability of FPE. Additionally noted was the antioxidant activity of FPE aqueous and methanolic extracts⁴¹. FPE seeds have been shown in multiple studies to have antioxidant properties in addition to its fruit.

4. Analgesic, Anti-pyretic, Anti-inflammatory Activity:-

FPE has potent analgesic and antipyretic properties as well. FPE's ethanolic and aqueous extracts significantly decreased the amount of yeast-induced hyperthermia in rats when administered at a high dosage (500 mg/kg, *i.p.*)⁴². The anti-inflammatory activities of the aqueous fraction of the methanolic extract of FPE were tested in rats with carrageenan and dextran-induced hind paw oedema. Both extracts prevented the acetic acid-induced writhing reaction in mice. The production of inflammatory mediators, including platelet-activating factor (PAF), leukotriene B4 (LTB4), and thromboxane B2 (TXB2), was also examined.

This anti-platelet reaction was ascribed to the presence of hydrolyzable tannins of low molecular weight, such as punigluconin, pedunculagin, emblicanin-A, and emblicanin-B. showed that *P. emblica* extract had analgesic effects in the acetic acid-induced writhing response and tail immersion test, as well as antipyretic benefits against hyperthermia generated by brewer's yeast.

The anti-inflammatory activities of the hydroalcoholic extract of FPE at a high dose of 700 mg/kg *b.w.* were revealed in a rodent investigation using carrageenan-induced acute inflammation and cotton pellet granuloma-induced chronic inflammation⁴³. The findings suggest that *P. emblica* could be effective in the treatment of inflammatory illnesses such as osteoarthritis. shown that *in vivo*, the ethanolic extract of FPE had analgesic efficacy in both postoperative and neuropathic pain models⁴⁴.

5. Anti Diabetic Activity:-

Diabetes mellitus, a prevalent endocrine metabolic disorder, has caused severe morbidity.

and mortality due to macrovascular complications (heart attack, and peripheral vascular disease) as well as microvascular effects (retinopathy, neuropathy, and nephropathy)⁴⁵. Type 2 diabetes, sometimes referred to as non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, is the most common form of the disease, accounting for 90–95% of cases that are characterised by inadequate insulin synthesis or use⁴⁶. The ethanolic extract of *P. emblica* effectively reduces blood glucose levels. By enhancing insulin sensitivity towards peripheral tissues, tannin, an efficient drug to inhibits adipogenesis and promote glucose uptake, is present in the ethanolic extract of *P. emblica*.

6. Anti Bacterial Activity:-

The antibacterial activity of *Phyllanthus emblica* was assessed by Jahan and Akter⁴⁷. The disc diffusion approach was used in this investigation. The methanolic extract of *P. emblica* was evaluated against Gram-positive, Gram-negative, and multidrug-resistant pathogens using a standard kanamycin disc at 500 µg/disc concentration. The findings showed that some bacteria, including *Shigella dysenteriae* (17 mm), *Staphylococcus aureus* (20 mm), and *Bacillus subtilis* (25 mm), were significantly inhibited by the ethanolic extract of PE. The disc diffusion method demonstrated the efficacy of *P. emblica*'s aqueous and ethanolic extracts against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*⁴⁸. When administered at doses of 50 mg/mL and 25 mg/mL, respectively, the methanolic extract of *P. emblica* completely killed AMR (antimicrobial-resistant) *S. Typhi* and *S. Enteritidis*⁴⁹.

7. Hepatoprotective Activity:-

P. emblica exhibited hepatocarcinogenic activities in the amlaki extract. In the rat model, the oral treatment of amla extract decreases the liver tumours caused by nitrosodiethylamine.

The amla plant's quercetin component reduced the liver damage and fibrogenic effects of dimethylnitrosamine⁵⁰. The hepatoprotective potential of the plant extracts and their components was examined. The results showed that WEPE dramatically decreased body weight, peritoneal fat, and epididymal fat in rats given a high-fat diet. It decreased steatosis by elevating adiponectin in adipocytes, lowering SREBP-1c in the liver, and increasing PPAR- α in the liver. This could explain why WEPE can reduce fat formation in the liver. These findings suggested that WEPE could be beneficial in the treatment of steatosis caused by an HFD⁵¹.

8. Nephroprotective Activity:-

P. officinalis's nephroprotective effects on oxidative stress-related kidney impairment in the ageing process. When given to aged rats, the plant extract was found to lower their elevated levels of urea nitrogen and serum creatinine⁵². Furthermore, elderly rats showed a considerable reduction in tail arterial blood pressure, serum thiobarbituric acid-reactive chemical levels, mitochondria, and renal homogenate. In another investigation, the plant's ethanol extract was examined for nephroprotective properties on a rat model. In rats fed ethylene glycol and ammonium chloride, the extract was demonstrated to reduce creatinine and urea levels at doses of 50, 100, and 150 mg/kg body weight⁵³.

9. Hypo-lipidemic activity:-

The anti-atherosclerotic and lipid-lowering properties of *P. emblica* fruits have been tested in rabbits given a diet rich in cholesterol. Fresh fruit juice reduced blood cholesterol, triglycerides, phospholipids, and LDL levels when taken at a dose of 5 mL/(kg•day) for 60 days. Phospholipid and cholesterol levels in the animal urine were found to be elevated, indicating that *P. emblica* might have also impacted the mechanism of absorption. According to another study, *P. emblica* also lowers the rabbits hepatic, aortic, and serum, cholesterol⁵⁴⁻⁵⁵.

10. Gastro-protective activity:-

The ethanolic extract of *P.emblica* dried fruit was investigated for its gastroprotective qualities in patients with gastrointestinal disorders. The evaluation included 30 patients in all, ten from each of the three groups. These three groups received 14 days of treatment with omeprazole, lactose (placebo), and ethanolic extract, respectively. 500 mg of the ethanolic extract per day was administered to the test group. Three times a day, participants in the negative control group (placebo) received 500 mg lactose pills. Finally, omeprazole at the suggested dosage of 40 mg per day was administered to the positive control groups. The ethanolic extract was found to

decrease pain, vomiting, sleep disturbances, and the repair of damaged mucosa⁵⁶.

11. Anti-Aging activity:-

The polyphenols in *P. emblica* fruit were discovered to have a significant protective effect against the ageing process in the *Caenorhabditis elegans* model. Its anti-aging qualities were demonstrated by increasing heat resistance and significantly lowering the activity levels of butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) by 45.38% and acetylcholinesterase by 34.71%⁵⁷.

Other activities include, *Phyllanthus emblica* act as laxative, anti-diarrhoeal, hair growth promoter, anti-hypertensive agent.

FIG:-Pharmacological activity of Phyllanthus emblica.

TRADITIONAL USES:-

In traditional medicine, balakka is a common ingredient. This plant has traditionally been used in India to treat anaemia, diabetes, liver, heart, and cancer. In several experimental diabetes models, chromium has strong antidiabetic effects. Additionally, chromium compounds can improve diabetic rats' fat metabolism. The balakka fruit is utilised as an anti-aging and TB treatment. Vitamin C, which has antioxidant qualities, and tannin, which has antimicrobial qualities, are both

present in balakka fruit. Furthermore, it has been shown and studied that balakka is an anti-cancer plant. Flavonoids and phenols from balakka plants have antioxidant qualities because they can absorb free radicals. Balakka's medicinal properties include its fruit for autos, candies, and jelly preserves, as well as its leather, which contains colourants that have been used as a blue dye in many kinds of fabrics, tanneries, furniture, agricultural instruments, and wood. According to the Wealth of India, *Phyllanthus emblica* seeds

have been proved to be effective treatments for bronchitis and asthma. Fruit juice released after harvesting is also used to treat eye irritation and as an ocular rinse. Traditionally, the fixed oil present in FPE was utilised as a hair tonic to promote pigmentation and hair development⁵⁸.

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CONCLUSION:-

P. emblica is a well-known Ayurvedic medicinal plant due to its numerous pharmacological applications in treating a variety of human ailments. Its most notable properties, however, are anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory action. The phytochemical research of *Phyllanthus emblica* found a rich variety of secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, tannins, polyphenols, and ascorbic acid. This indigenous fruit, which is profoundly ingrained in traditional medicine, has been shown to be an extraordinary source of bioactive compounds with great therapeutic features. *Phyllanthus emblica* is a prospective source of bioactive compounds with various pharmacological properties. While this review is useful in understanding its potential benefits, further research and clinical trials are required to fully realise this amazing plant species' therapeutic potential. the significance of *Phyllanthus emblica* in the realm of natural medicine and promotes additional research in the pursuit of improved healthcare solutions.

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